

Modeling of Thermal Processes Associated to an Electric Arc

Authors : Hatem Allagui, Fathi Ghodbane

Abstract : We are interested by the studying of the thermal effects of the electric arc on the breaker apparatus contacts for forecasting and improving the contact durability. We will propose a model which takes account of the main influence factors on the erosion contacts. This phenomenon is very complicated because the amount of ejected metal is not necessarily constituted by the whole melted metal bath but this depends on the balance of forces on the contact surface. Consequently, to calculate the metal ejection coefficient, we propose a method which consists in comparing the experimental results with the calculated ones. The proposed model estimates the mass lost by vaporization, by droplets ejection and by the extraction mechanism of liquid or solid metal. In the one-dimensional geometry, to calculate of the contact heating, we used Green's function which expresses the point source and allows the transition to the surface source. However, for the two-dimensional model we used explicit and implicit numerical methods. The results are similar to those found by Wilson's experiments.

Keywords : electric arc, thermal effect, erosion, contact, durability

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